

University of Groningen

Different notions of community in energy community legislation

Hoops, Björn

Published in:
Journal of Energy and Natural Resources Law

DOI:
[10.1080/02646811.2025.2540695](https://doi.org/10.1080/02646811.2025.2540695)

IMPORTANT NOTE: You are advised to consult the publisher's version (publisher's PDF) if you wish to cite from it. Please check the document version below.

Document Version
Version created as part of publication process; publisher's layout; not normally made publicly available

Publication date:
2025

[Link to publication in University of Groningen/UMCG research database](#)

Citation for published version (APA):
Hoops, B. (2025). Different notions of community in energy community legislation. *Journal of Energy and Natural Resources Law*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02646811.2025.2540695>

Copyright

Other than for strictly personal use, it is not permitted to download or to forward/distribute the text or part of it without the consent of the author(s) and/or copyright holder(s), unless the work is under an open content license (like Creative Commons).

The publication may also be distributed here under the terms of Article 25fa of the Dutch Copyright Act, indicated by the "Taverne" license. More information can be found on the University of Groningen website: <https://www.rug.nl/library/open-access/self-archiving-pure/taverne-amendment>.

Take-down policy

If you believe that this document breaches copyright please contact us providing details, and we will remove access to the work immediately and investigate your claim.

Downloaded from the University of Groningen/UMCG research database (Pure): <http://www.rug.nl/research/portal>. For technical reasons the number of authors shown on this cover page is limited to 10 maximum.

Different notions of community in energy community legislation

Björn Hoops

To cite this article: Björn Hoops (05 Sep 2025): Different notions of community in energy community legislation, Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law, DOI: [10.1080/02646811.2025.2540695](https://doi.org/10.1080/02646811.2025.2540695)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02646811.2025.2540695>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 05 Sep 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Different notions of community in energy community legislation

Björn Hoops * *Full Professor of Private Law and Sustainability at the Faculty of Law of the University of Groningen (The Netherlands). From April 2022 to March 2024 he was Marie Curie Fellow at the University of Turin. Email: b.hoops@rug.nl.*

This article contributes to the literature an analytical framework for determining and comparing legislative notions of ‘energy community’. The framework consists of membership, financial investment, decision-making, activities and benefits as expressions of community. The article further adds a comparison of the notions of community in EU minimum-harmonisation directives and member states’ transpositions on energy communities. The analysis produces diverging notions of community. Some notions are contradictory as member states move in opposite directions with respect to corporate influence over energy communities. Other notions move in the same direction but limit to varying degrees the room for energy communities to regulate themselves.

Keywords: energy community; IEMD; RED II; community of place; community of interest; process dimension; outcome dimension

1. Introduction

As solar panels and other sources of renewable energy can be installed in many different places, they can support a decentralised and local energy transition for the decarbonisation of our economies.¹ Compared to large power plants, renewable energy projects render it substantially easier and more attractive for private citizens to participate in the generation of energy. Citizen involvement in the energy sector, in turn, is likely to give the energy transition an extra boost by mobilising hitherto inaccessible private capital and reducing local resistance to often controversial projects such as windfarms.² A collective form of citizen involvement are energy communities, in which citizens pool their resources to generate, consume, sell and/or store renewable energy. Worldwide, policymakers and scholars expect energy communities not only to make renewable energy widely accessible and provide energy

*Current affiliation: Extraordinary Professor, University of the Western Cape (South Africa)

- 1 Stephanie Lenhart and others, ‘Comparing and Contrasting the Institutional Relationships, Regulatory Frameworks, and Energy System Governance of European and US Electric Cooperatives’ in Andrea M Feldpausch-Parker and others (eds), *Routledge Handbook of Energy Democracy* (Routledge 2021) 34–5
- 2 See, for instance, Anne-Lorène Vernay, Carine Sebi and Fabrice Arroyo, ‘Energy Community Business Models and their Impact on the Energy Transition: Lessons Learnt from France’ (2023) 175 *Energy Policy* 113473; Valeria Jana Schwanitz and others, ‘Statistical Evidence for the Contribution of Citizen-Led Initiatives and Projects to the Energy Transition in Europe’ (2023) 13 *Scientific Reports* 1342; Fleur Goedkoop and Patrick Devine-Wright, ‘Partnership or Placation? The Role of Trust and Justice in the Shared Ownership of Renewable Energy Projects’ (2016) 17 *Energy Research & Social Science* 135, at 135–7

security, but also to activate citizen engagement, support local cohesion and development, and alleviate energy poverty.³

The EU seeks to promote collective citizen involvement in energy generation by recognising ‘citizen energy communities’ (CEC) under the Internal Electricity Market Directive (IEMD) and ‘renewable energy communities’ (REC) under the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II).⁴ IEMD and RED II primarily define energy communities through requirements for their internal organisation.⁵ The 27 EU member states have to transpose the directives and in particular the definitions of energy communities into their legal order. EU and national legislation on energy communities does not force citizen-led energy projects to become ‘energy communities’ in a legal-technical sense. By offering the right to share energy and easier access to the energy market, the legislation does incentivise energy projects to adjust their internal organisation to the legal definition of ‘energy community’.⁶

The EU directives on energy communities and their national transpositions establish potentially diverging legal notions of community. The goal of this contribution is to develop and apply a framework for analysing and comparing such notions. Applying the functional method of comparative law,⁷ this contribution identifies the societal issues addressed by the definitions, namely membership requirements for, financial investment in, decision-making in, activities of, and benefit distribution by energy communities, and determines the differences and similarities in how to address these issues. The goal of this contribution is thus descriptive, while elsewhere in this special issue the normative underpinnings and desirable definitions of energy communities at the intersection of energy cooperation and energy justice are explored.⁸ This framework enables researchers and rule-makers to compare the characteristics of energy communities in the EU and beyond. In giving an account of the diverging notions of community in energy community legislation, it provides a basis for non-legal inquiries into the advantages and drawbacks of each legal definition with respect to policy goals such as the flourishing of energy community and the promotion of the energy transition and decarbonisation.

This contribution adds a detailed examination of the legislative definitions of community to the literature on energy communities. Social scientists define communities through sustained interaction and an emotional bond between community members, while disagreeing on the bases and sources of community.⁹ Energy community scholars

³ See, in addition to the sources in note 2, Amollo Ambole, Kweku Koranteng, Peris Njoroge and Douglas Logedi Luhangala, ‘A Review of Energy Communities in Sub-Saharan Africa as a Transition Pathway to Energy Democracy’ (2021) 13(4) Sustainability 2128

⁴ European Parliament and Council Directive (EU) 2019/944 of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU [2019] OJ L158/125 (IEMD), art 16; European Parliament and Council Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources [2018] OJ L328/82 (RED II), art 22

⁵ IEMD, art 2 no 11; RED II, art 2 no 16

⁶ Shubhra Chaudhry, Arne Surmann, Matthias Kühnbach and Frank Pierie, ‘Renewable Energy Communities as Modes of Collective Prosumership: A Multi-Disciplinary Assessment Part II – Case Study’ (2022) 15(23) *Energies* 8936

⁷ Mathias Siems, *Comparative Law* (CUP 2014) 13ff

⁸ Maciej M Sokolowski, Madeline Taylor and Iwo Buller, ‘Seven Pillars of Energy Cooperation: An Energy Justice-Driven Framework for Energy Communities and Energy Cooperatives’ (2025) 43 *Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law* 1

⁹ Kenneth C Bessant, *The Relational Fabric of Community* (Palgrave Macmillan 2018); Roger Cotterrell, *Living Law: Studies in Social and Legal Theory* (Routledge 2008) 17–18

have identified and compared numerous notions of energy community in the literature, but left out legislative notions of energy community.¹⁰ A distinctly legal perspective is needed as the legislative definition of community goes beyond interactions and emotional bonds and tends to be more complex due to the expectations that policymakers and scholars have of energy communities. To legal science, this contribution adds a methodologically rigorous framework and comprehensive examination of the legal definitions of energy community to existing piecemeal analyses and comparisons.¹¹

This contribution shows that the EU directives on energy communities and their national transpositions offer a variety of partially diverging notions of community, urging future inquiries into their suitability to promote energy communities. To arrive at this conclusion, this contribution is structured as follows. Section 2 first sets out the various definitions of '(energy) community'. Then, drawing on the societal issues addressed by the definitions, it formulates common questions to be asked to determine the notion of energy community in each legal order. Section 3 answers these questions with respect to the EU directives and the member states' transpositions. Section 4 concludes this contribution. Section 5 contains an appendix with a list of the examined legislation in the member states and a list of deviations in transpositions from the EU directives on energy communities.

2. A legal deconstruction of energy community and framework for assessing legislative notions of community

The term 'community' inspires hope for collaboration, familiarity, security and warmth, but scholars propose a variety of partially conflicting definitions of 'energy community'.¹² What is clear is that communities are webs of social relations and interaction that are denser and more intense than between two random people who are not part of the same community.¹³ Communities bring about rights and obligations between members and between members and the community as a whole, albeit not necessarily in a legal sense. The bases for this connection, its size and scale, and its functions and objectives are diverse and disputed, as discussed in sub-section 2.1 focusing on energy cooperatives as a potential example of communities.

As sub-section 2.2 shows, scholars not only describe and delimit communities from other social phenomena. Scholars make prescriptions on how citizen initiatives in the energy sector *should be* to qualify as energy communities, advocating in particular for participatory governance and distributive justice as cornerstones.¹⁴ These quality standards turn 'energy community' into a cachet reserved for selected citizen initiatives within a larger group that may equally be considered communities. Such quality

10 Thomas Bauwens and others, 'Conceptualizing Community in Energy Systems: A Systematic Review of 183 Definitions' (2022) 156 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 111999, 2

11 Michael Krug and others, 'Implementing European Union Provisions and Enabling Frameworks for Renewable Energy Communities in Nine Countries: Progress, Delays, and Gaps' (2023) 15(11) *Sustainability* 8861

12 Bauwens and others (n 10) 2

13 Bessant (n 9) 2; Cotterrell, *Living Law* (n 9) 17–18

14 See, eg, Gordon Walker and Patrick Devine-Wright, 'Community Renewable Energy: What Should It Mean' (2008) 36(2) *Energy Policy* 497–500

standards have also found their way into legislation. IEMD and RED II regulate the internal organisation of energy communities in their definitions.¹⁵

As the EU directives show, the law is a means to encourage or even enforce compliance with normative prescriptions within human relations. To perform this instrumental function, the law needs to connect to a definition of ‘energy community’. What sets the law apart from other social sciences is the law’s inability to connect directly to intangible and invisible facts of life, such as the mental bond between community members.¹⁶ As sub-section 2.3 elaborates, this entails that the law has to find expressions of energy communities, particularly for the elements inaccessible to the law.

Sub-section 2.4 presents the expressions of energy communities used in section 3 to determine and compare the notions of community under member states’ energy community legislation, and sketches the underlying sources of these expressions, to which the law cannot connect directly. Far from being a general legal theory of community, these expressions provide the components of a legislative definition of ‘energy community’ and a framework for analysing different configurations of these expressions in energy community legislation.

2.1. *Community in sociology*

To distinguish communities from other forms of collective social life, scholars point to the personal character and intensity of the social relations within a community.¹⁷ The community’s web of social relations also consists of a concrete group of people, which may or may not be easy to define and delimit. In cooperatives producing renewable energy, for instance, the members invest in, decide on, and/or manage renewable energy installations together to consume or sell the energy.

These dense social relations set communities apart from a society and other forms of collective social life characterised by less personal and intense relations with a potentially amorphous group of people, such as the general public.¹⁸ While some authors consider ‘community’ as even including the state, for example to discuss the obligations of the individual vis-à-vis the state,¹⁹ the term ‘community’ used here refers to a web of more personal and more intense social relations.

Communities have an objective and tangible dimension in the form of stable and sustained interaction between members, creating formal or informal structures of social relations. Energy cooperatives are examples of communities that have formalised structures through the establishment of a legal person recognised by law. Communities also have a subjective and intangible dimension through a sense of attachment and belonging.²⁰

Scholars debate the bases and connecting factors for stable and sustained interaction between the members and their sense of belonging and attachment. Traditionally,

15 IEMD, art 2 no 11; RED II, art 2 no 16

16 Cotterrell, *Living Law* (n 9) 27–28

17 Robin Means and Simon Evans, ‘Communities of Place and Communities of Interest? An Exploration of their Changing Role in Later Life’ (2012) 32 *Ageing & Society* 1300, at 1301

18 *ibid* 1301

19 Gregory S Alexander and Eduardo M Peñalver, ‘Properties of Community’ (2009) 10 *Theoretical Inquiries in Law* 127

20 Roger Cotterrell, ‘A Legal Concept of Community’ (1997) 12(2) *CJLS/RCDS* 75, at 78

sociologists distinguish between communities of place, communities of interest, and communities of identity.²¹ These connecting factors are not mutually exclusive, but can be intertwined and reinforce each other within one community.²² The literature on energy communities often uses a simplified distinction between place- and interest-based communities.²³

Communities of place are created by regular personal contact in a locality in which the members live or to which they otherwise feel attached.²⁴ While in the past, communities were always considered bound to places, globalisation and technological innovations such as virtual interaction through the internet and fast modes of transport have fuelled a despatialisation of communities and enabled the creation of placeless social networks.²⁵ That said, scholars still predominantly associate energy communities with a certain place,²⁶ and empirical research indicates that most citizen initiatives in the energy sector are bound to a place.²⁷

Communities of interest are rooted in shared concerns and/or values of community members.²⁸ A specific variant of community of interest is the community of practice, characterised by common activities and/or exchanging experiences, knowledge and information about a shared endeavour or profession.²⁹ Energy cooperatives are communities of interest in that members pursue the common goal of generating renewable energy through joint investments, decision-making and activities.

Communities of identity are rooted in emotion-laden bonds of attachment and belonging based upon, for example, common culture, kinship, language, places and/or traditions.³⁰ Sustained social interaction over long periods can be both the result and the source of communities of identity.³¹ Energy cooperatives that involve their members in energy generation and supply them with energy will eventually become part of the members' identity.

Scholars propose various hybrid forms of connecting factors combining characteristics of the traditional three types.³² Applied to energy cooperatives, the most relevant hybrid concepts are 'intentional communities', in which people choose to live and work together to pursue a common goal drawing on common beliefs, values, and/or practices;³³ 'communities of choice', established to pursue environmental sustainability

21 Means and Evans (n 17) 1301

22 Bessant (n 9) 12; Means and Evans (n 17) 1302

23 Jarra Hicks and Nicola Ison, 'An Exploration of the Boundaries of "Community" in Community Renewable Energy Projects: Navigating Between Motivations and Context' (2018) 113 *Energy Policy* 523, at 524 and 527

24 Bessant (n 9) 5–7

25 *ibid* 25

26 Bauwens and others (n 10) 7

27 Björn Hoops, 'EU Directives on the Internal Governance of Energy Communities and their Exclusionary Effects' (2024) 17(3) *Journal of World Energy Law & Business* 147, 164–5

28 Bessant (n 9) 7–10

29 *ibid* 8

30 *ibid* 10–11

31 CJ Calhoun, 'Community: Toward a Variable Conceptualization for Comparative Research' (1980) 5 *Social History* 105–29

32 See, for an overview, Bessant (n 9) ch 1

33 Paul Hoggett, 'Contested Communities' in Paul Hoggett (ed), *Contested Communities: Experiences, Struggles, Policies* (Policy Press 1997) 3–16

and/or economic cooperation;³⁴ and ‘instrumental communities’, representing a convergence of interests in pursuing a common goal.³⁵

In terms of size and scale, it is clear that communities of place and identity are limited, while communities of interest are less exclusive and can therefore involve more people.³⁶ In practice, the size and scale of energy cooperatives vary, ranging from small placed-based to large interest-based cooperatives.³⁷

Scholars also identify three functions of energy communities, which interact with the connecting factors.³⁸ Energy communities are an actor giving the members agency to pursue a shared objective effectively. For example, an energy cooperative can acquire a renewable energy installation and distribute and/or sell the generated energy. They also serve as a framework for social relations, in local or more geographically dispersed webs. More tangibly, the members of energy cooperatives may discuss in the General Assembly and generate their own energy. Finally, energy communities create and/or sustain a common identity of the members through shared values and practices. For instance, energy cooperatives are driven by, and instil a belief in, promoting the energy transition and climate protection.

2.2. *The prescriptive dimension of energy community*

The research presented up to this point omits the content of the interactions or emotional bonds within energy communities. However, as acknowledged in commons scholarship, communities are not automatically equitable or benign, but that does not make them less of a community from a descriptive perspective.³⁹

The literature on energy communities has a distinct prescriptive dimension that sets normative standards for groups who want to qualify as energy communities. A prominent example is the literature on ‘energy democracy’, which examines and promotes the democratisation of the energy system through broad-based active and egalitarian citizen participation.⁴⁰ The standards concern the activities, purposes and benefit distribution, membership and decision-making of citizen initiatives in the energy sector. Beyond the scholarly debate, the EU directives on energy communities incorporate these standards, denying the status of energy community to all who do not meet them. In the following, this sub-section sketches these standards with reference to scholarly literature and the EU directives.

2.2.1. ACTIVITIES, PURPOSES AND BENEFIT DISTRIBUTION

Scholars argue that the activities of energy communities should be small-scale projects in renewable energy generation, storage and distribution, to promote a decentralised energy

³⁴ Bessant (n 9) 9

³⁵ Cotterrell, *Living Law* (n 9) 24

³⁶ Means and Evans (n 17) 1302

³⁷ Björn Hoops, ‘Two Tales of the Energy Commons Through the Lens of Complexity’ (2024) 25(1) *Global Jurist* s 2.3

³⁸ Bauwens and others (n 10) 2

³⁹ Fritjof Capra and Ugo Mattei, *The Ecology of Law: Toward a Legal System in Tune with Nature and Community* (Berrett-Koehler Publishers 2015) 164; David Bollier, *Think Like a Commoner: A Short Introduction to the Life of the Commons* (New Society Publishers 2014) 162–3

⁴⁰ Andrea M Feldpausch-Parker and others (eds), *Routledge Handbook of Energy Democracy* (Routledge 2021)

transition.⁴¹ Through these activities, energy communities should not or at least not primarily pursue financial profits, but instead counter concentration on the energy market, strengthen local economies, empower vulnerable people and alleviate inequality.⁴² Accordingly, the EU directives require that energy communities primarily provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for the members or for the local areas where they operate.⁴³ This rule primarily excludes commercial enterprises that aim at generating profits for their shareholders.

This rule also has an impact on benefit distribution. Although profits remain permissible, they generally have to be re-invested in the community.⁴⁴ For the rest, the EU directives remain silent on how benefits are to be distributed within the energy community. The literature calls for an empowerment of vulnerable households, demanding that lower energy prices or other benefits substantially accrue to vulnerable households.⁴⁵

2.2.2. MEMBERSHIP: OPEN, LOCAL, INCLUSIVE AND FREE FROM CORPORATE INFLUENCE

Concerning membership in an energy community, many scholars take a nuanced approach to openness. Although energy communities should generally be open to those seeking admission, many scholars advocate for local and inclusive energy communities free from corporate influence. More specifically, some scholars assert that only place-based energy communities can be truly inclusive and empower the members to take decisions autonomously.⁴⁶ Others note that there are also other ideal forms than local commons.⁴⁷ Scholars call for inclusive energy communities empowering disadvantaged households against the background of rampant energy poverty.⁴⁸ At the same time, energy communities should exclude powerful corporate entities because such entities may otherwise abuse them.⁴⁹

The EU directives require energy communities to be open, but allow non-arbitrary and non-discriminatory criteria for admission.⁵⁰ The directives in all probability allow for the exclusion of people who do not have a sufficiently strong connection with the area.⁵¹

41 Bauwens and others (n 10) 3. However, in practice, many energy communities upscale their activities: Daniel Petrovics, ‘Diverse Scaling Strategies of Energy Communities: A Comparative Case Study Analysis of Varied Governance Contexts’ (2024) 19 *Earth System Governance* 100203

42 Matthew J Burke, ‘Energy Commons and Alternatives to Enclosures of Sunshine and Wind’ in Andrea M Feldpausch-Parker, Danielle Endres, Tarla Rai Peterson and Stephanie L Gomez (eds), *Routledge Handbook of Energy Democracy* (Routledge 2021) 202–3; Goedkoop and Devine-Wright (n 2) 135–7

43 IEMD, art 2 no 11; RED II, art 2 no 16

44 Joshua Roberts, ‘What Are Energy Communities Under the EU’s Clean Energy Package?’ in Frans HJM Coenen and Thomas Hoppe (eds), *Renewable Energy Communities and the Low Carbon Energy Transition in Europe* (Palgrave Macmillan 2021) 30

45 Burke (n 42) 202–3; Sören Becker, ‘The State or the Citizens for Energy Democracy?’ in Andrea M Feldpausch-Parker, Danielle Endres, Tarla Rai Peterson and Stephanie L Gomez (eds), *Routledge Handbook of Energy Democracy* (Routledge 2021) 168

46 Burke (n 42) 206; Lenhart and others (n 1) 46

47 Bollier (n 39) 155–6; Julie L MacArthur and M Derya Tarhan, ‘Institutionalizing Energy Democracy’ in Andrea M Feldpausch-Parker and others (eds), *Routledge Handbook of Energy Democracy* (Routledge 2021) 174

48 Burke (n 42) 202–3; Becker (n 45) 168

49 Burke (n 42) 202–3; MacArthur and Tarhan (n 47) 181. cf Roberts (n 44) 34

50 IEMD, art 2 no 11 and art 16(1)(a); RED II, art 2 no 16

51 Maciej M Sokołowski, ‘Renewable and Citizen Energy Communities in the European Union: How (not) to Regulate Community Energy in National Laws and Policies’ (2020) 38(3) *Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law* 289, at 298

A requirement of place-based energy communities only applies insofar as RED II stipulates that effective control of renewable energy communities is reserved for members from the area in which the renewable energy installations are located. To make energy communities more inclusive of vulnerable households, RED II compels member states to ensure access for low-income and vulnerable households.⁵² With respect to corporate influence, RED II excludes energy companies, large enterprises and non-local authorities from membership in renewable energy communities.⁵³ IEMD, by contrast, does not impose membership restrictions.

2.2.3. DECISION-MAKING

There are diametrically opposed views in the literature on who should take what decisions within an energy community. The EU directives limit the influence of individual members through an autonomy requirement and reserve effective control for members, even members in the proximity of the renewable installations under RED II, while excluding non-local authorities and enterprises of certain sizes from effective control.⁵⁴

It is disputed what effective control, autonomy and proximity mean. A formal approach to effective control is to have members elect a management board from the pool of active members or available professionals and hold the managers to account, but to leave most decisions, including on renewable energy installations, to the managers. In order to have effective control, citizens, local authorities and enterprises of a certain size would then only have to hold 51 per cent of votes in an assembly of members.⁵⁵ For the energy community to be autonomous, no individual member would have more than 33 per cent of all votes.⁵⁶ By contrast, another approach advocates for more broad-based active participation by requiring a decisive voice for members in managing the energy community.⁵⁷ As regards proximity, the prevailing view is that it refers to *physical* vicinity,⁵⁸ potentially excluding interest-based energy communities.⁵⁹

2.3. *A legal definition of energy community?*

To lawyers, ‘community’ is an important, yet in part inaccessible concept. In private relationships between individuals, private law creates communities of property based on the individuals’ agreement, for example in condominium (strata title) or matrimonial

52 RED II, art 22(4)(f). cf Lea Diestelmeier, ‘Citizen Energy Communities as a Vehicle for a Just Energy Transition in the EU – Challenges for the Transposition’ (2021) 1 Oil, Gas & Energy Law Intelligence 1, at 10

53 RED II, art 2 no 16(b) and art 22(1); cf Roberts (n 44) 33–4

54 IEMD, art 2 nos 7 and 11; RED II, art 2 no 16

55 Jens Lowitzsch, ‘Consumer Stock Ownership Plans (CSOPs) – The Prototype Business Model for Renewable Energy Communities’ (2020) 13(1) *Energies*, art 118, 6

56 *ibid* 6

57 Roberts (n 44) 34–5

58 Mehmet Efe Biresellioglu and others, ‘Legal Provisions and Market Conditions for Energy Communities in Austria, Germany, Greece, Italy, Spain, and Turkey: A Comparative Assessment’ (2021) 13 *Sustainability*, art 11212, 7 and 9

59 Stefano Moroni and Luca Tricarico, ‘Distributed Energy Production in a Polycentric Scenario: Policy Reforms and Community Management’ (2018) 61 *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* 1973, at 1976–7

property law.⁶⁰ The law regulates the establishment, management, external relations and dissolution of this community, but, unlike other social sciences, does not investigate or attach consequences to the underlying sources thereof. The law also provides for legal persons, such as associations and cooperatives, as potential legal vehicles for voluntary communities, such as energy cooperatives. By contrast, the law of succession⁶¹ and citizenship law create involuntary communities.

Legal literature widely discusses ‘community’ in various contexts, also going beyond the distinction between voluntary and involuntary communities. This contribution presents one example from legal pluralism. Cotterrell puts forward a legal concept of community along the lines of the sociological definition of community.⁶² This concept could justify (semi-)autonomous self-regulation by a community that is at the moment, and possibly even after the recognition of their right of self-regulation, primarily regulated by outsiders.⁶³ Energy communities, even though not discussed by Cotterrell, are a case in point. The law on legal persons gives them autonomy to regulate their own affairs, implicitly recognising a limited right of self-regulation. The EU directives on energy communities, by contrast, restrict this right by imposing normative standards for their internal governance, albeit in exchange for certain privileges on the energy market.⁶⁴

What the outlined legal examples and Cotterrell’s concept have in common is that they create ‘community’ as a legal fact, if not entity, that gives rise to rights and obligations. The challenge facing lawmakers and scholars alike is to express characteristics that constitute a ‘community’ through terms that legal practitioners are able to apply. The legal examples connect to tangible facts that can be determined relatively easily, such as an agreement, the death of a person, or citizenship. By contrast, Cotterrell refers to still-ascertainable facts such as long-time sustained interactions but also to emotional bonds created by places, interest and/or identities. As Cotterrell himself admits, values and beliefs are hard to translate into rules, and affection may even defy rational analysis.⁶⁵

What Cotterrell describes is the inability of the law to connect directly to intangible and invisible facts of life. To define an ‘energy community’ in law through a place, interest or identity would be foolish. Not every inhabitant of a place will join a local energy community, and lawyers cannot ascertain whether living in a place has actually motivated the individual to join. The same applies to interest and identity, products of the mind that cannot be determined unless the individual directly or indirectly expresses them. This means that the sociological definition of community cannot be directly used for the legal definition of ‘(energy) community’ or as a framework for comparing different notions of community in law. That said, sociological work can still immensely benefit legal theories explaining why the law is the way it is or how it should be.

A framework for analysing different notions of community in law needs to connect to tangible expressions of ‘community’. These expressions serve as proxies for the presence

60 Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*; BW), art 1:94 and 5:106(4) BW

61 BW, art 3:189(2) and 4:227

62 Cotterrell, ‘A Legal Concept of Community’ (n 20) 80–2

63 *ibid* 75 and 79

64 cf Gordon Walker and others, ‘Trust and Community: Exploring the Meanings, Contexts and Dynamics of Community Renewable Energy’ (2010) 38(6) *Energy Policy* 2655, at 2662, arguing for tailor-made regulation.

65 Cotterrell, *Living Law* (n 9) 27–8

of a community. As the compared pieces of national legislation are all based on the EU directives, the expressions will take into account the aspects regulated by the directives. This framework still acknowledges the role of the sociological definition of ‘community’ in that its elements are connecting factors or sources of ‘community’. The following sub-section explains the expressions and sketches the sources.

2.4. *Expressions of energy communities as components of a definition*

To determine and compare different notions of ‘community’ in law, an analytical framework needs to provide common questions that must be answered with respect to all legal systems. Each question is linked to an expression of ‘community’. This methodological approach is in essence an application of the functional method of comparative law.⁶⁶

Primarily drawing on the definition of energy communities under IEMD and RED II, this sub-section introduces and elaborates on the following expressions of ‘community’ and related questions: rules (discussed in sub-section 2.4.1); membership (2.4.2); financial investment (2.4.3); decision-making (2.4.4); activities/operation (2.4.5); and benefit distribution (2.4.6). This list of expressions of ‘community’ does not purport to be exhaustive, but covers the main expressions under the EU directives and the examined national legislation. The answers to the questions about these expressions together form the notion of ‘energy community’ and can be understood as minimum quality standards for recognising and conferring privileges upon citizen initiatives in the energy sector.

The sub-section not only sets out these expressions, but also possible connections between them. For instance, there may be an overlap between financial investments, benefits and/or decision-making. Those who invest more in the ‘community’ may receive more benefits and/or have more control over the community.

This contribution distinguishes the expressions from ‘sources of community’. If present, such sources operate as connecting factors contributing to the formation of a community by promoting joint activities and/or identities. The literature on energy communities discusses sources of community as part of a broader category of ‘drivers’.⁶⁷ The most relevant sources of community are a common place,⁶⁸ financial interests,⁶⁹ shared values⁷⁰ and other intrinsic and/or extrinsic motivations such as trust,⁷¹ already existing

⁶⁶ Siems (n 7) 13ff

⁶⁷ See, for instance, Frank Pieter Boon and Carel Dieperink, ‘Local Civil Society Based Renewable Energy Organisations in the Netherlands: Exploring the Factors that Stimulate their Emergence and Development’ (2014) 69(C) *Energy Policy* 297–307; Breffni Lennon and Niall Dunphy, ‘Sustaining Energetic Communities: Energy Citizenship and Participation in an Age of Upheaval and Transition’ (2024) 14 *Scientific Reports* 3267

⁶⁸ Bessant (n 9) 5–7

⁶⁹ Thomas Bauwens, ‘Analyzing the Determinants of the Size of Investments by Community Renewable Energy Members: Findings and Policy Implications from Flanders’ (2019) 129 *Energy Policy* 841, 849ff; Jens Lowitzsch, ‘Investing in a Renewable Future – Renewable Energy Communities, Consumer (Co-)Ownership and Energy Sharing in the Clean Energy Package’ (2019) 9(2) *Renewable Energy Law and Policy Review* 14, 25; Thomas Bauwens, ‘Explaining the Diversity of Motivations Behind Community Renewable Energy’ (2016) 93(C) *Energy Policy* 278, at 286–7

⁷⁰ Bauwens and others (n 10) 2; Bauwens, ‘Analyzing the Determinants’ (n 69) 849ff; Bauwens, ‘Explaining the Diversity’ (n 69) 286–7; Bessant (n 9) 8

⁷¹ Bauwens, ‘Explaining the Diversity’ (n 69) 286–7

Figure 1. The expressions of ‘community’ (author’s own design).

community identities,⁷² autonomy and self-efficacy.⁷³ These sources interact with the expressions of ‘community’ and relating legislative requirements, thereby limiting or broadening the members’ scope for shaping each expression. For instance, requirements that the members have their residence or seat in a certain place not only limit the total group of potential members but also put an emphasis on the source ‘place’, which may encourage local members to join and thereby increase the actual number of members.

Figure 1 shows the expressions discussed in the following sub-sections.

2.4.1. RULES

The rules follow an agreement between the founding members and are the formal basis of the community and its expressions. The rules formally shape and govern the other

⁷² Bassent (n 9) 5; Bauwens, ‘Explaining the Diversity’ (n 69) 286–7

⁷³ Binod Prasad Koirala and others, ‘Trust, Awareness, and Independence: Insights from a Socio-Psychological Factor Analysis of Citizen Knowledge and Participation in Community Energy Systems’ (2018) 38 *Energy Research & Social Science* 33, at 38; Boon and Dieperink (n 67)

expressions. However, when making the rules, the founding members first determine the other expressions and then shape the rules accordingly. Their successors will have to abide by these rules unless the necessary majority changes them.

2.4.2. MEMBERSHIP

A community consists of its members, which makes them an important expression of the community. In this analysis, the members of the ‘community’ are those who are formal members in the legal vehicle of the ‘community’, if any, and/or may formally participate in the making of the community’s rules. For instance, the members of a cooperative are members for the purposes of this analysis. This definition of members excludes, for example, hired professionals, political supporters, and donors who have not become formal members and cannot otherwise formally participate in rule-making. One should not forget, though, that they often make essential contributions to communities and may exert influence indirectly.

The overall issue surrounding this expression is who may become a member. The first question pertaining to this expression is whether there are groups of entities excluded from membership. This question relates to the exclusion of certain powerful entities from membership under RED II. The second question refers to the legislative requirements for membership, such as the residence or seat in a certain area. This question is inspired by the openness and proximity requirements.

Both questions draw on the work of Walker and Devine-Wright. They distinguish between the process and outcome dimensions of energy communities.⁷⁴ The process dimension includes the question of who is involved in the energy community.

2.4.3. FINANCIAL INVESTMENTS

Members can provide equity or other forms of financing, for example through contributions to a development trust, to a community through investments and thereby enable the community to act, expressing a bond with the other members. The main question relating to financial investments by members is the extent to which energy community legislation condones obligations for members to invest money. An additional requirement for membership may be that energy communities must not charge excessive amounts because RED II requires that energy communities be inclusive of vulnerable households.⁷⁵

2.4.4. DECISION-MAKING

While the community appears in the outside world through its activities, these activities are based on internal decisions, making the decisions themselves an expression of the community. The most important decisions taken by energy-generating energy communities on their activities are what renewable energy installations to acquire, where to operate them, how to finance them, and what to do with the generated energy. There are two questions linked to decision-making. First, who may take these decisions?

⁷⁴ Walker and Devine-Wright (n 14) 498–9

⁷⁵ RED II, art 22(4)(f)

Second, if not all members take these decisions, who appoints the decision makers and to whom are the decision makers accountable? In the literature, Walker and Devine-Wright emphasise the importance of who runs and has influence over the energy community as part of its process dimension.⁷⁶ Inspiration for these questions also comes from the EU directives reserving effective control for members and the exclusion of certain groups of powerful entities from effective control.

A particular connection exists between decision-making, membership and investment. Supposedly, only members can have a say in appointing decision makers. The two questions point to the extent to which membership and decision-making overlap, the issue of how many members actually participate in decision-making, and to the extent to which an investment translates into decision-making power.

2.4.5. ACTIVITIES

This contribution focuses on energy-generating citizen initiatives. The joint activities of generating and consuming or selling renewable energy as an expression of ‘community’ can give rise to a bond and suggests that such citizen initiatives are also, or at least can be, communities of practice.⁷⁷ This expression of ‘community’ begs an inquiry into the extent to which such citizen initiatives may entrust external parties or single members with the control and/or operation of the renewable energy installations. This question is also inspired by the process dimension of energy communities and the question of who runs and who has influence over the energy community.⁷⁸

In this respect, the activities are closely related to decision-making. If the control and operation of the renewable energy installations is partially outsourced, this decision may limit the scope for manoeuvring for the decision makers.

2.4.6. BENEFIT DISTRIBUTION

Finally, the sharing of benefits from the activities is an expression of ‘community’. Such benefits may be the sharing of energy at a lower than market price or the net annual profit made from selling the energy. The questions are who may benefit and what share in the benefits they may receive. These questions reflect the outcome dimension of energy communities discussed by Walker and Devine-Wright.⁷⁹ The prohibition of financial profit as a primary purpose of energy communities and the required inclusivity of energy communities under the EU directives also inspire these questions.

The expression of benefit distribution has strong links with decision-making, membership and investment. Decision-making includes decisions on the distribution of benefits. As regards membership, the analysis of this expression inquires into the extent to which members are entitled to claim the community’s benefits. The answers to these questions do not address donations made by the energy community or the hiring of professionals, who, of course, also benefit from the activities of the energy

⁷⁶ Walker and Devine-Wright (n 14) 498–9

⁷⁷ Bessant (n 9) 8

⁷⁸ Walker and Devine-Wright (n 14) 498–9

⁷⁹ *ibid*

Table 1. Expressions of ‘community’ and pertinent questions (author’s own design).

Expression	Question
Membership	Does the energy community legislation exclude certain groups of entities from membership? Does it set other requirements for membership?
Investment	To what extent does the energy community legislation allow for mandatory investments by members?
Decision-making	Who may take decisions on behalf of the energy community under the energy community legislation? Who appoints the decision makers and to whom are they accountable under that legislation?
Activities/ operation	To what extent may an energy community outsource the control and operation of renewable energy installations under energy community legislation?
Benefit distribution	Under the energy community legislation, who may enjoy the benefits of the energy community and are there minimum and/or maximum shares?

community. Finally, investment may directly translate into an entitlement to benefits, raising the question of whether higher investments may lead to more benefits.

2.4.7. FINAL OVERVIEW

Table 1 summarises the expressions of ‘community’ and the pertinent questions.

3. Different notions of community in energy community legislation

This section determines and compares the answers in the EU directives and their national transpositions regarding the expressions of community. Also, it sketches how the expressions appeal to different sources of community. This section does not distinguish between notions of citizen or renewable energy communities. As regards the transpositions, the section primarily highlights deviations from the directives. The appendix provides an overview of these deviations. This research has drawn on the transposition tracker on rescoop.eu to get an overview of the relevant legislation and regulations. An English translation or the original version of the directives and transpositions has been examined to conduct this analysis. The appendix contains a list of the examined legal texts.

3.1. Membership

To prevent corporate abuse of energy communities as vehicles for financial interests,⁸⁰ RED II excludes energy companies, large enterprises, and non-local authorities from membership in renewable energy communities. IEMD, by contrast, does not impose such membership restrictions for citizen energy communities.

Most member states simply copy–paste this choice of the EU co-legislators. By contrast, some impose stricter requirements or undercut the protection against corporate abuse. Stricter regimes apply in Latvia,⁸¹ where large enterprises are excluded from *all* energy communities, as well as in Croatia, where medium-sized and large enterprises are excluded from citizen energy communities.⁸² These regimes restrict the notion of community to a smaller group of entities as potential members and express that medium-sized and/or large enterprises cannot form part of it without the citizen initiative losing their community character. On the other hand, such a choice may enlarge the pool of potential members by appealing to autonomy, trust and values as sources of community. People may view the pursuit of financial interests by corporations as undermining the cohesion and goals of the citizen initiative.

By contrast, Hungary,⁸³ Romania⁸⁴ and Italy⁸⁵ have introduced a rather lenient regime under their transpositions. Large enterprises may become members of renewable energy communities. This notion of community tolerates corporate interests among its members, possibly to benefit from these entities' expertise. Such a choice is likely to attract large enterprises through the source of financial interests, but may also discourage other potential members as these financial interests may contravene existing trust, prevalent values, or the pursuit of autonomy.

Under RED II, the proximity requirement, interpreted as geographical proximity, applies only to effective control of renewable energy communities, not to membership. Some member states do impose proximity requirements for membership or at least discourage non-residents from joining the community. Croatian,⁸⁶ Finnish⁸⁷ and Portuguese⁸⁸ law subject membership in energy communities to being connected to the same transformer station. In Greece, 51 per cent of the members must be residents or property owners, or have their seat in the region of the headquarters of the energy community.⁸⁹ More indirectly, Austria,⁹⁰ Italy,⁹¹ Poland,⁹² Spain⁹³ and Wallonia⁹⁴ discourage non-residents from joining the energy community by limiting the sharing of the generated energy and/or even other activities to those members connected to the same transformer station.

These proximity requirements or incentives for or against membership introduce a place-based notion of community that is barely traceable to the EU directives and, at

81 Energy Law, art 17(8), not differentiating between the two types of energy communities.

82 Electricity Market Act (Official Gazette, no 111/21), art 26(2). See also the Slovak Act 251/2012, art I(11a)(1), which seems to ban large and medium-sized enterprises from citizen energy communities, but it is uncertain whether the provision applies to effective control or membership.

83 Act 86 of 2007, § 66/B(1) and (1a)

84 Government Emergency Ordinance of 29 November 2022, art 2 no 18

85 Decree Law 199/2021, art 31(1) *littera* b and c

86 Electricity Market Act, art 26(1) and (2), regarding citizen energy communities. Strangely, Renewable Energy Law, art 52, contains no such restriction for renewable energy communities.

87 Decree 767/2021, s 3

88 Decree Law no 15/2022, art 189(1)(a), regarding renewable energy communities.

89 Act 5037/2023, art 47(3) and 90

90 Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz (EIWOG), § 16c(2), regarding renewable energy communities; citizen energy communities only receive subsidies for electricity fed into the grid.

91 Renewable energy communities: Decree Law 199/2021, art 8(1)(b) and 31(2) *littera* c. Citizen energy communities: Decree Law 210/2021, art 14(8)

92 Energy Act 1997, art 11zk(2)

93 The participation radius is 2,000 m: Royal Decree Law 20/2022 of 27 December 2022, art 18

94 Decree of 5 May 2022, art 35nonies(1)

first glance, limit the pool of potential members. On the other hand, this choice appeals to place, already existing identities, and, potentially, trust as sources of community, which may recruit local people more effectively than if more members came from outside the municipality or region.

3.2. *Investment*

RED II obliges the member states to ensure that renewable energy communities be accessible for vulnerable and low-income households. This task raises the question of whether member states regulate the minimum investment of members in the energy community. High minimum investments potentially deter vulnerable and low-income households from joining and make the energy community more exclusive.⁹⁵

A comparative study has shown that 23 out of 27 transpositions at most pay lip service to this obligation.⁹⁶ Only four out of 27 member states, Greece, Italy, Lithuania and Spain, take concrete measures to make energy communities more inclusive. However, they do not address the minimum investment, but rely upon incentives for energy communities to admit vulnerable households and/or the role of local authorities in ensuring the representativeness of the energy community.

Thus, it appears by and large irrelevant to the notion of community throughout the EU whether the community is inclusive of vulnerable and low-income households. Exclusionary minimum investments will not prevent citizen initiatives from qualifying as energy communities. This finding is difficult to reconcile with the demands in the literature to alleviate energy poverty and to distribute the benefits of the energy transition equitably. On the other hand, it may appeal to existing trust and pursuit of autonomy as sources of community if legislation and regulations do not impose the admission of certain households.

3.3. *Decision-making*

To prevent corporate abuse of energy communities as vehicles for corporate interests, the EU directives reserve effective control for people, local authorities and small enterprises. In renewable energy communities, medium-sized enterprises also may exercise effective control. Moreover, renewable energy communities must be autonomous. What autonomy and effective control mean is rather uncertain. Autonomy vaguely requires limits to the powers exercised by individual members to promote the community's independence.⁹⁷ The possible meanings of effective control range from accountability of managers to the members to broad-based active participation in management by the members.⁹⁸ The member states thus still need to answer the questions of who may take decisions

⁹⁵ Lea Diestelmeier, 'The Role of Energy Communities in Facilitating Sustainable Energy Democracy' in Ruven Fleming, Kaisa Huhta and Leonie Reins (eds), *Sustainable Energy Democracy and the Law* (Brill 2021) 130; MacArthur and Tarhan (n 47) 181

⁹⁶ Björn Hoops, 'The Clash of the Energy Commons' (2024) 33(3) *European Energy and Environmental Law Review* 115, at 119

⁹⁷ Roberts (n 44) 37–8; Maciej M Sokołowski, 'Models of Energy Communities in Japan (Enekom): Regulatory Solutions From the European Union (Rescoms and Citencoms)' (2021) 30(4) *European Energy and Environmental Law Review* 149, 154–5

⁹⁸ See subsection 2.2 above.

on renewable energy installations and who appoints and controls these decision makers. These answers will have a considerable impact on the notion of community as the decision makers affect all members and largely define the appearance of the community to the outside world.

The member states have generally copy-pasted the exclusion of certain groups of entities from effective control. There are, however, a few exceptions. Italy has expanded the groups of entities that may have effective control by including non-profit organisations and research and teaching institutions.⁹⁹ Many such entities will still be excluded from effective control of renewable energy communities, though, due to the requirement of geographical proximity. The transposition in the Netherlands,¹⁰⁰ by contrast, is stricter in that it also excludes medium-sized enterprises from effective control in renewable energy communities.

Czechia, Denmark, Hungary and Lithuania have concretised the exclusion of legal persons from effective control. Czech law denies voting rights to energy companies, medium-sized and large enterprises, and non-local authorities, and even to non-local members in renewable energy communities.¹⁰¹ Under Lithuanian law, natural persons, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), local authorities, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) from the area must hold 51 per cent of the votes in the assembly of members.¹⁰² Under Danish law, persons whose main economic activity is a large-scale commercial activity or an activity in the energy sector may not become managers or representatives of the energy community.¹⁰³ Under Hungarian law, persons who hold majority ownership in a legal person engaged in the energy sector or are senior executives of such a legal person may not exercise management powers in the energy community on their own.¹⁰⁴

When concretising effective control and autonomy, most member states focus on the relationship between the members. Croatia,¹⁰⁵ Greece¹⁰⁶ and Ireland¹⁰⁷ have made the one-head-one-vote principle compulsory for the assembly of members. In addition, Croatia and Greece limit the maximum number of shares of individual members to 40 per cent or 20 per cent of all shares, respectively.¹⁰⁸ In Wallonia, there is a maximum voting share of 50 per cent per member.¹⁰⁹ France limits the maximum voting share of individual members to ten per cent and of enterprises and their employees to 40 per cent.¹¹⁰ Czech law also provides for a ceiling of ten per cent per member.¹¹¹ The adoption of the one-head-one-vote principle can also be implicit in limiting the available legal vehicles to legal persons that tend to follow this principle. For instance, while Austria

⁹⁹ Decree Law 210/2021, art 3(3) *littera* b; Decree Law 199/2021, art 31(1) *littera* b

¹⁰⁰ Energy Act, art 2.4(1)(c)

¹⁰¹ Energy Act, § 20b(2)(c) and (3)(d)

¹⁰² Renewable Energy Law, art 20²(2) no 2, with respect to renewable energy communities.

¹⁰³ Decree no 1069 of 30 May 2021, art 6(2)

¹⁰⁴ Act 86 of 2007, § 66/B(5) and (6)

¹⁰⁵ Electricity Market Act, art 26(3), with respect to citizen energy communities.

¹⁰⁶ Act 5037/2023, art 48(2) and 90

¹⁰⁷ Renewable Energy Support Scheme 1, Terms and Conditions, s 2.1

¹⁰⁸ Act 5037/2023 (Greece), art 48(1) and 90; Croatian Electricity Market Act, art 26(4), with respect to citizen energy communities.

¹⁰⁹ Decision of the Government of 17 March 2023, art 11

¹¹⁰ Decree no 2023–1287 of 26 December 2023, art 1

¹¹¹ Energy Act, § 20b(2)(c), with respect to citizen energy communities.

allows capital companies to be energy communities,¹¹² Poland¹¹³ and Lithuania¹¹⁴ exclude for-profit companies, and Slovenia sets cooperatives as the standard legal form for citizen energy communities.¹¹⁵

While it is clear who may or may not exercise effective control, most member states remain silent on the relationship between members and managers. Latvia explicitly reserves some decision-making powers for members. Members shall participate in decisions that confer influence on, or actual control in, the energy community.¹¹⁶ Such decisions concern ownership rights of the energy community and the composition of governing bodies. The acquisition of renewable energy installations thus seems to fall in the domain of the members. Flanders and Slovenia also ensure that members have a say in the composition of management bodies.¹¹⁷

This analysis produces different notions of community in the member states. To varying degrees, the member states share the notion that decision-making in a community is largely free from powerful corporate or government interests. Denmark has adopted the most concrete and strictest version by excluding large enterprises and energy companies from management positions. These choices show that membership and investment as expressions of community do not directly translate into decision-making power. This could appeal to trust and autonomy as sources of community and enhance the community's potential, but also reduce the role of financial interest as a source of community.

The rules on the relationship between members reveal diverging notions of community. While some member states insist on the one-head-one-vote principle and/or specify a maximum voting share, others remain silent on this issue. On one side of the continuum, a community must consist of members with an equal say, irrespective of how large their financial investment has been. Such a relationship between the expressions of membership, investment and decision-making expresses democratic values and may appeal to trust and values as sources of community. On the other side of the continuum, the weight of each member's vote depends on their financial investment, even though there may be a maximum voting share. This direct translation of investment into decision-making may appeal to financial interest as a source of community, but may weaken values and trust.

The allocation of powers between members and managers also reflects diverging notions of community. An ideal of direct democracy, which has not been made mandatory by any member state, would translate membership directly into decision-making power. However, it seems that most member states permit an indirect democracy in which managers take major decisions on behalf of the members and there is less of an overlap between membership and decision-making. Each of these notions may, depending on the context, appeal to pre-existing identities, values and trust as sources of community.

¹¹² Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz (EAG), § 79(2); EIWOG, § 16b(2)

¹¹³ Energy Act 1997, art 11zi

¹¹⁴ Renewable Energy Law, art 20²(2) no 2, with respect to renewable energy communities.

¹¹⁵ Act 3349 of 2021 (ZOEE), art 24

¹¹⁶ Energy Law, art 17(10)

¹¹⁷ Flemish Energy Decree, art 4.8.1(1); Slovenian ZOEE, art 37(4), with respect to citizen energy communities.

3.4. *Activities*

As the activities are the main expression of citizen initiatives in the outside world, the question is whether energy communities may entrust external parties or single members with the control and/or operation of the renewable energy installations. The directives largely remain silent on this point. Only RED II seems to presuppose that renewable energy communities own and develop their installations themselves.¹¹⁸ Some member states have concretised the control of the renewable energy installations. Irish law follows a notion of community that requires the control of the renewable energy installation through ownership. In a joint venture, the renewable energy community must own at least 51 per cent of the energy generator or the project's assets.¹¹⁹ In Flanders, renewable energy communities must be the owner of their installations, while for citizen energy communities a right to use the installations is sufficient.¹²⁰ While control in the form of ownership is required, Flemish renewable energy communities do not necessarily run their installations themselves because Flemish law allows them to entrust third parties with operating the installation.¹²¹

In other member states, it is sufficient for energy communities to have a right to use the generated energy. Italy,¹²² Portugal,¹²³ Slovenia¹²⁴ and Wallonia¹²⁵ fall into this category. They follow a notion of community with less control over their own activities.

Collaboration with experts at the expense of less control may enhance the productivity of the energy community. Such success may strengthen the common identity of the members and their financial interests as sources of community. More control over the activities, by contrast, may appeal to the pursuit of autonomy as a source of community.

3.5. *Benefit distribution*

The prohibition of financial profits as the primary purpose under the EU directives raises the issue of who may benefit and to what extent from the activities of the energy community. The legislation in most member states merely states that the primary purpose of energy communities must be to generate economic, environmental or social benefits for the members and/or the surrounding local communities. Such a requirement paints an energy community that is embedded in its natural or social environment, and thus demands a broad group of beneficiaries beyond the formal members of the energy community. However, it does not specify the minimum benefits to be generated for this group or, as disbursements of profits remain possible, limit the benefits received by single or all members.

There are three member states that specify what needs to happen with the energy community's profits and limit the financial benefits reaped by members. Latvia prohibits the disbursement of profits if the energy community is a capital company.¹²⁶ Slovakia limits

¹¹⁸ RED II, art 2(16)(a)

¹¹⁹ Renewable Energy Support Scheme 1, Terms and Conditions, s 7.1.1(a)

¹²⁰ Energy Decree, art 4.8.2(1) and 4.8.4(1)

¹²¹ *ibid*, art 4.8.4(1)

¹²² Decree Law 199/2021, art 31(2)(a); Decree Law 210/2021, art 14(8)(d)

¹²³ Decree Law No 15/2022, art 189(1)(b), regarding renewable energy communities.

¹²⁴ ZOEE, art 37(4), with respect to citizen energy communities.

¹²⁵ Decree of 5 May 2022, art 2 nos 2quinquies, 35undecies(1) and 4

¹²⁶ Energy Law, art 17(7)

disbursements of financial profits to formal members to 50 per cent.¹²⁷ The rest thus has to stay in the energy community and can be reinvested. Greece even limits disbursements to 20 per cent of the profits.¹²⁸ Such measures create a notion of community that limits the extent to which members may take money out of the collective purse for private purposes and requires the use of collective means for collective goals.

3.6. *Concluding overview*

The EU directives paint the picture of energy communities as generally open to everybody, with the possibility for the community to set non-arbitrary and non-discriminatory entry requirements for members. The RED II does ban certain powerful entities from membership to avoid the community being taken over by corporate or non-local government interests. In terms of investment, the directives do not impose an obligation for members to invest. Despite an obligation for member states to ensure the inclusion of vulnerable households under RED II, there is no maximum for the amount that energy communities may ask from vulnerable and low-income members. Under the directives, effective control over the community is supposed to be free from powerful corporate and non-local government interests. RED II more generally excludes non-local interests from effective control. Apart from this exclusion of powerful entities, the directives do not dictate a certain allocation of voting shares or powers within the community. In particular, the managers of the community may come from outside the community. The same applies to the control over the renewable energy installations, which can but need not be owned and operated by the community themselves. Finally, the benefits should accrue to members and surrounding communities through, for example, environmental protection, local economic development, and/or lower energy prices, but the directives do not generally preclude the community from disbursing the surpluses to the members.

The directives give a very rough notion of community. The only hard choice they make is the exclusion of powerful corporate and non-local government interests from effective control or even membership, to ensure that members are not demoted to, respectively, passive shareholders or consumers of public services. For the rest, the directives leave the majority of choices to the member states and/or the communities themselves. For instance, energy communities can be exclusively local but do not need to be. Broad-based active participation by members in the management of the community is but one governance option. Potentially, this framework leaves plenty of room for self-regulation.

Many member states have resorted to copy-pasting in their transposing legislation and thus follow the rough notion of community under the directives. Some member states have filled the space left by the directives with more detailed notions of community. Residence requirements for membership or energy sharing in renewable energy communities or even both types of energy community point to the notion of communities being local. Other member states exclude further corporate and non-local government interests from membership or effective control, entrench the one-head-one-vote principle, and/or adopt restrictions on the involvement of powerful interests in the management, pointing to a notion of communities being more democratic and member-driven

¹²⁷ Act 251/2012, art I(11a)(4)

¹²⁸ Act 5037/2023, art 54 and 90

than required by the directives. Going in the other direction, a few member states expand the opportunities for enterprises to obtain membership and/or decision-making power. Some member states require a community to have full control over their activities through ownership, while others explicitly allow for the outsourcing of activities. Only very few member states ensure the secondariness of financial goals by limiting the disbursement of surpluses to members, pointing to a notion of not-for-profit communities.

Mostly, the member states omit to enshrine a coherent notion of community and adopt piecemeal rules that still leave many choices to the energy communities. It appears that Croatia offers the most coherent notion of a democratic and local energy community through the additional exclusion of medium-sized and large enterprises from citizen energy communities, a residence requirement for energy sharing, and the adoption of the one-head-one-vote principle.

4. Conclusion

This contribution has provided and applied a novel framework for analysing and comparing the notions of ‘energy community’ in energy community legislation. Communities are webs of intense social relationships characterised by sustained interaction and an emotional bond of attachment. Social scientists have long debated the bases and sources of community. To legal scientists, community is accessible where this term may explain the content or effect of a law. To lawmakers and those who apply the law, by contrast, community is largely inaccessible as it refers to intangible and invisible facts of life. To refer to a community, lawmakers need to translate the desired characteristics of a community into tangible proxies.

Regarding energy communities, the list of desired characteristics is long due to the goal of promoting the small-scale and citizen-driven generation of renewable energy. The implementation of these characteristics under IEMD and RED II leads to more complex legal notions of community than those discussed in other disciplines. Drawing on these EU directives and the literature, this contribution has identified the main issues addressed by this notion – membership requirements for, financial investment in, decision-making in, activities of, and benefit distribution by energy communities – and reformulated them as expressions of community in order to investigate how the legislation of each member state addresses each issue. At the EU level, the notion of community under the directives remains rough. The directives primarily exclude corporate and non-local government interests from effective control or even membership, but for the rest leave plenty of room for the communities to regulate themselves.

Inquiring how member states regulate each expression of community, this contribution has found some contradictory notions of community. For instance, while some member states exclude more enterprises from membership and/or effective control than required by the directives, others open the door farther for large enterprises to become members of even renewable energy communities. For the most part, however, while some member states introduce more detailed notions of local, democratic and/or not-for-profit communities, others stick to the EU directives. These different notions of community in energy community legislation do not contradict each other, but they limit to varying extents the range of options for energy communities to design their own notion.

This contribution has provided a framework for rule-makers and researchers to analyse legislative notions of ‘energy community’ in the EU and beyond. Uncovering diverging notions in EU legislation and its transpositions in the member states, it has

laid the groundwork for policymakers and researchers to assess the advantages and disadvantages of the approaches to each expression of community in light of policy goals, such as a decentralised energy transition and the decarbonisation of our economies and societies.

Acknowledgements

This contribution is a result of the project ‘Private Law and the Energy Commons’, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 101024836. The author expresses his gratitude to Paulina Ryszkowska and Yulia Sergeeva for excellent research assistance. An early version of this contribution was presented at the conference ‘Private Law in the Energy Commons’ at the University of Turin on 27 March 2024. The author is indebted to the participants for their comments.

Disclosure statement

The author reports there are no competing interests to declare.

ORCID

Björn Hoops <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1073-8004>

Appendix

Table A1. Examined transpositions into national law per country (author’s own design).

Member state	Examined transpositions
Austria	Electricity Industry and Organization Act 2010 (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz 2010; EIWOG), in particular §§ 16b-16e EIWOG; Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz (EAG).
Brussels (Belgium)	Ordinance of 17 March 2022 (Ordonnantie tot wijziging [...] met het oog op de omzetting van richtlijn 2018/2001 en richtlijn 2019/944 van 17 maart 2022).
Bulgaria	Amendment of 13 October 2023 to Law on Energy from Renewable Sources (ЗАКОН ЗА ЕНЕРГИЯТА ОТ ВЪЗОБНОВЯЕМИ ИЗТОЧНИЦИ)
Croatia	Law on the Electricity Market (ZAKONA O TRŽIŠTU ELEKTRIČNE ENERGIJE), in particular Art. 26; Law on Renewable Energy Sources and Highly Efficient Cogeneration (ZAKONA O OBNOVLJIVIM IZVORIMA ENERGIJE I VISOKOČINKOVITIJ KOGENERACIJ).
Cyprus	Law 130(I)/2021 on the Regulation of the Electricity Market (ΝΟΜΟΣ ΠΟΥ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΠΕΙ ΓΙΑ ΤΗ ΡΥΘΜΙΣΗ ΤΗΣ ΑΓΟΡΑΣ ΗΛΕΚΤΡΙΣΜΟΥ); Law 107(I)/2022 on the Promotion and Encouragement of the Use of Renewable Energy Sources (ΝΟΜΟΣ ΠΟΥ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΠΕΙ ΓΙΑ ΤΗΝ ΠΡΟΩΘΗΣΗ ΚΑΙ ΕΝΘΑΡΡΥΝΣΗ ΤΗΣ ΧΡΗΣΗΣ ΤΩΝ ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΙΜΩΝ ΠΗΓΩΝ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ).
Czechia	Act on the conditions of business and on the performance of state administration in the energy sector and on the amendment of certain laws (Energy Act) (Zákon o podmínkách podnikání a o výkonu státní správy v energetických odvětvích a o změně některých zákonů (energetický zákon))

(Continued)

Table A1. Continued.

Member state	Examined transpositions
Denmark	Decree (BEK) No 1069 of 30 May 2021 (Bekendtgørelse om VEfællesskaber og borgerenergifællesskaber og forholdet mellem VEfællesskaber og borgerenergifællesskaber og elhandelsvirksomheder og kollektive elforsyningsvirksomheder); Act on the Promotion of Renewable Energy (lov om fremme af vedvarende energi).
Estonia	Electricity Market Act (Elektrituruseadus); Electricity Management Act (Energiamajanduse korralduse seadus).
Finland	Decree 767/2021.
Flanders (Belgium)	Energy Decree (Decreet van 2 april 2021 tot wijziging [...] tot gedeeltelijke omzetting van richtlijn 2018/2001 [...] tot omzetting van richtlijn (EU) 2019/944 [...]).
France	Decree (Décret) No 2023–1287 of 26 December 2023.
Germany	No transposition, except for a definition of ‘Bürgerenergiegesellschaften’ in § 3 No 15 of the Renewable Energy Act 2023 (Gesetz für den Ausbau erneuerbarer Energien 2023).
Greece	Act 5037/2023.
Hungary	§§ 3 and 66/B, Act 86 of 2007.
Ireland	Renewable Energy Support Scheme 1.
Italy	Decree Law 210/2021 (Decreto legislativo 8 novembre 2021, n. 210); Decree Law 199/2021 (Decreto legislativo 8 novembre 2021, n. 199).
Latvia	Amendments to the Energy Law of 14 July 2022 (Grozījumi Enerģētikas likumā), Art. 17 Energy Law.
Lithuania	Renewable Energy Law (Lietuvos Respublikos atsinaujinančių išteklių energetikos įstatymas).
Luxembourg	Act of 9 June 2023 (Loi du 9 juin 2023 modifiant la loi modifiée du 1er août 2007 relative à l’organisation du marché de l’électricité), in particular Art. 1(7bis) of the Electricity Market Act.
Malta	Subsidiary Legislation 545.35 on the Promotion of Energy from Renewable Sources Regulations.
The Netherlands	Energy Act (Energiewet).
Poland	Amendments of 28 July 2023 to the Energy Law (Prawo energetyczne).
Portugal	Decree Law (Decreto-Lei) No 15/2022 of 14 January 2022.
Romania	Emergency Ordinance (ORDONANȚĂ DE URGENȚĂ) of 29 November 2022; Emergency Ordinance of 28 December 2021.
Slovakia	Act (Zákon) 256/2022 of 22 June 2022, amending Act 251/2012.
Slovenia	Electric Supply Act 3349 of 2021 (Zakon o oskrbi z električno energijo; ZOE).
Spain	Royal Decree Law (Real Decreto-ley) 20/2022 of 27 December 2022.
Sweden	No transposition.
Wallonia (Belgium)	Decree of 5 May 2022 (Décret du 5 mai 2022 modifiant diverses dispositions en matière d’énergie dans le cadre de la transposition partielle des directives européennes du ‘Clean Energy Package’).

Table A2. Overview of the examined issues, the regulation of these issues under the EU directives, and deviating or concretising transpositions in the EU member states (author's own design).

Issue	Response under EU directives	Deviating/concretising Transpositions into national law
Excluded entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewable energy community (REC): energy companies, large enterprises, non-local authorities; - Citizen energy community (CEC): none. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Croatia: medium-sized and large enterprises excluded from CECs. - Hungary, Italy, Romania: large enterprises may join RECs. - Latvia: large enterprises also excluded from CECs.
Membership requirements	<p>Non-arbitrary and non-discriminatory requirements permitted.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Croatia, Finland, Portugal: proximity requirement (connection to same transformer station). - Greece: 51 per cent of members must reside or have their seat in area. - Austria, Italy, Poland, Spain, and Wallonia: energy sharing requires connection to the same transformer station.
Mandatory investment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REC: no direct provision, but accessibility for low-income and vulnerable households. - CEC: no provision. 	<p>All member states: no provisions on minimum investments.</p>
Decision makers	<p>Competing opinions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Members directly manage; - Members appoint managers. <p>In any case: independence from single members.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Croatia: individual member holds no more than 40 per cent of shares. - Denmark: large enterprises and energy companies may not assume managerial or representative positions. - Flanders, Slovenia: members participate in appointing managers. - Greece: individual member holds no more than 20 per cent of shares. - Hungary: shareholders and senior executives of energy companies may not exercise management rights on their own. - Latvia: members participate in decisions conferring influence or actual control over the community.

(Continued)

Table A2. Continued.

Issue	Response under EU directives	Deviating/concretising Transpositions into national law
Appointment and accountability of decision makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REC: by local people, SMEs, and authorities. - CEC: by natural persons, small enterprises, and local authorities. - Both: independence from single members. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Croatia, Greece, Ireland: one head, one vote. - Czechia: non-local members, energy companies, and SMEs do not have voting rights; voting share of one member is not greater than ten per cent. - France: voting share of one member must not be greater than ten per cent (40 per cent for enterprises and their employees). - Italy: local non-profit organisations and research and teaching institutions may have effective control. - Lithuania: natural persons, SMEs, local authorities and local NGOs hold 51 per cent of the votes in assembly. - Netherlands: excluding medium-sized enterprises from effective control in RECs. - Wallonia: voting share of one member must not be greater than 50 per cent.
Outsourcing installations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - REC: possibly ownership and development of installation required. - CEC: no provision. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flanders: RECs must be owner of the installation; CECs must have use right. Outsourcing of operations is permitted. - Ireland: community must own at least 51 per cent of the installation in a joint venture. - Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, Wallonia: right to use the generated energy sufficient.
Beneficiaries and distribution	<p>Economic, environmental, and social benefits must dominate. Reinvestment of profits in community outweighs disbursement to members.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greece: no more than 20 per cent of profits may be disbursed to members. - Latvia: prohibition of disbursements of profits by capital companies. - Slovakia: no more than 50 per cent of profits may be disbursed to members.